

Study on the Citrate Complex of Strontium

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The citrate complex of strontium has been investigated by the pH titration method at pH 7.2 to 7.3. The equilibrium constant of the reaction:

is determined to be 5.23×10^2 .

Hastings and co-workers (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1934, 107, 351) found the formation constant of strontium citrate by biological assay method to be 5.012×10^2 . Schubert and Richter (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 4259) studied the strontium citrate complex by using cation exchangers and found the formation constant of Sr Cit^{-} to be 6.457×10^2 .

EXPERIMENTAL

An $M/20$ strontium perchlorate solution was prepared as follows. A very pure sample of strontium carbonate was added in excess to an $M/10$ perchloric acid so that some of the strontium carbonate was left undissolved. The solution was boiled for a few minutes at $40-50^\circ$ to remove CO_2 . The solution was cooled and allowed to settle for 3 to 4 hours for attaining equilibrium. Finally the solution was filtered to a dry bottle and the filtrate estimated for strontium content.

Expt. I.—Curve A (Fig. 1) represents the results obtained by titrating 200 c.c. of a solution containing 0.025 g. mole of citric acid and curve B represents that of another solution of the same volume containing 0.025 g. mole of citric acid and 0.0025 g. mole of strontium perchlorate against $N\text{-NaOH}$ at 32.5° .

$N\text{-NaOH}$ added (c.c.).
FIG. 1

Expt. II.—Curve A (Fig. 2) represents the results obtained by titrating 100 c.c. of a solution containing 0.025 g. mole of sodium perchlorate and curve B that of another 100 c.c. of a solution containing 0.025 g. mole of sodium perchlorate and 0.00125 g. mole of strontium perchlorate against 0.1M sodium citrate at 32.5°.

FIG. 2.

Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain a constant ionic strength in both the solutions.

TABLE I

pH.	[Ct] _A or [Cit ³⁻] _A × 10 ⁴ .	[Ct] _B × 10 ³ .	[Sr (ClO ₄) ₂] × 10 ² .	[SrCit ⁻] × 10 ³ .	[Sr ²⁺] × 10 ³ .	K × 10 ⁻² .
7.25	3.985	0.9902	1.238	0.5917	11.79	1.260
7.26	4.976	1.9610	1.228	1.4640	10.80	2.725
7.26	4.976	2.9130	1.213	2.4160	9.71	5.000
7.27	4.976	3.6610	1.204	3.1640	8.88	7.161
7.27	5.474	4.7620	1.191	4.2150	7.69	10.000

DISCUSSION

The results obtained in *expt. I* are similar to those obtained in the calcium citrate systems (Pattnaik and Pani, this *Journal*, 1961, **38**, 229). There is no indication of liberation of acid. The formation of the complex resulting in removal of the citrate ligand is, however, indicated. The horizontal distance between the two curves increases in the beginning, then decreases, and finally becomes negligible after pH 6.0.

In *expt. II* the results are again similar to those obtained in the calcium citrate system (*loc. cit.*). There is an appreciable rise in this case also in the pH after the addition of very nearly 1 g. mole of sodium citrate per g. mole of strontium perchlorate. This is a clear indication of the formation of SrCit⁻, which is a stable complex.

Calculation of the Equilibrium Constant

In *expt. II* the complex SrCit⁻ is formed with increasing addition of sodium citrate. The formation of the complex is nearly complete when 1 g. mole of sodium citrate is added

per g. atom of strontium. The reaction is represented by equation (1) and the equilibrium constant by equation (1-1)

$$\frac{[\text{SrCit}^{-}]}{[\text{Sr}^{2+}] \times [\text{Cit}^{3-}]} = K \quad \dots \quad (1-1)$$

$[\text{Cit}]_A$, $[\text{Cit}]_B$, $[\text{Sr}(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$, $[\text{SrCit}^{-}]$, $[\text{Cit}^{3-}]$ and $[\text{Sr}^{2+}]$ were calculated as determined in the case of calcium citrate complex (*loc. cit.*) and formation constant of SrCit^{-} from Sr^{2+} and Cit^{3-} was calculated by equation (1-1). The values are recorded in Table I.

The mean value of K is 5.23×10^2 . This is in good agreement with the values obtained by many authors.

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